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The Trust of Building Manufacturers in Europe

Between March 2022 and December 2022, it decreased on average by 698%

The Eurostat calculates the value of the building manufacturers' trust in Europe.

Ranking of European countries by the value of the building manufacturers' trust in Europe in December 2022. Slovenia is in the first place for value of December 2022 with a value of 24.3, followed by Ireland with a value of 20, 6 units, followed by Spain with a value of 17.5 units. In the middle of the ranking there are Slovakia with a value equal to -2.9 units, followed by Malta with a value equal to -4.3 units, followed by Portugal with a value equal to -5.5 units. Finland closes the ranking with a value equal to -16.6 units, followed by Greece with a value equal to -23.3 units and Poland with a value equal to -24.4 units.

Ranking of European countries for the value of the percentage variation of the building manufacturers' trust between March and December 2022. Spain is in the first place for the value of the percentage variation of the self-confidence of the builders between March and December 2022 with a value equal to 94.44% equal to an amount of 8.50 units, followed by Slovakia with a value of 73.87% equal to a value of 8.20 units, followed by Turkey with a value of 61.93% equal to an amount of 12.20 units. In the middle of the standings there are Croatia with an amount of -19.10% equal to an amount of -1.70 units, followed by Ireland with a value of -26.95% equal to an amount of -7.60 units and from Poland with a value equal to -30.48% equal to an amount of -5.70 units. Hungary closes the ranking with a value equal to -1093.33% equal to an amount of -16.40 units, followed by the Czech Republic with a value equal to -1.800% equal to -7.20 units and Greece with -2.218.18% equal to an amount of -24.40 units.

Clusterization with K-means algorithm optimized with the Elbow method. Below is a clusterization with the K-means algorithm with the Elbow method. Four Clusters are identified so composed or:

- Cluster 1: Poland, Cyprus, Greece, Lithuania, Latvia, Denmark;
- Cluster 2: Belgium, France, Italy, Sweden, Germany, Croatia, Austria, Malta, Estonia, Spain;
- Cluster 3: Bulgaria, Turkey, Slovakia, Finland, North Macedonia, Albania, Czech Republic, Hungary, Portugal, Montenegro, Serbia, Romania;
- Cluster 4: Slovenia, Luxembourg, Netherlands, Ireland.

From a metric point of view, considering the size of the clusters median it is possible to identify the following hierarchical system or: $C4 = 16.6 > C2 = 1.25 > C3 = -7.55 > C1 = -15.4$. From a geographical point of view, it is possible to verify the non-geographical continuity of the countries of the Cluster 4 which, with the exception of Slovenia, coincide with countries with a strong orientation to the preparation of a favorable tax system towards capital investments. Cluster 4 countries follow the countries of Cluster 2 or the countries of Western Europe, followed by Eastern Europe's countries. The countries of Cluster 1 close or a composite of countries not attributable to the same geographical area within the European Union are close.

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Network Analysis with Manhattan's distance. A Network Analysis is presented below with the distance of Manhattan. Three structures are identified with complex networks. There is a complex network structure between the following countries:

- Lithuania has a connection with Latvia for a value of 0.59 units;
- Latvia has a connection with Lithuania with a value of 0.59 units and with Bulgaria for a value of 0.48 units;
- Bulgaria has a connection with Latvia for a value of 0.48 units and with Turkey for a value of 0.56 units;
- Turkey has a connection with Bulgaria for a value equal to an amount of 0.56 units and with Albania for a value of 0.53 units;
- Albania has a connection with Turkey for a value of 0.53 units.

There is an additional complex network structure consisting of three countries or:

- Portugal has a connection with Serbia for a value of 0.37 units and with the Czech Republic for a value of 0.49 units;
- Serbia has a connection with Portugal equal to an amount of 0.37 units and with the Czech Republic equal to an amount of 0.44 units;
- The Czech Republic has a connection with Serbia equal to an amount of 0.44 units and with Portugal equal to an amount of 0.49 units.

There is a third complex network structure consisting of the following countries or:

- Austria has a connection with Sweden for a value of 0.66 units;
- Sweden has a connection with Austria for a value of 0.66 units, with France equal to an amount of 0.62 units, with Belgium for a value of 0.46 units and with Italy equal to an amount of 0.59 units;
- France has a connection with Sweden for a value of 0.62 units, with Italy equal to an amount of 0.47 units and with Belgium equal to an amount of 0.54 units;
- Italy has a connection with Sweden for a value of 0.59 units, with France for a value of 0.46 units and with Belgium for a value of 0.49 units;
- Belgium has a connection with France equal to an amount of 0.54 units, with Sweden equal to an amount of 0.46 units, with Italy for a value of 0.49 units and with Germany for a value of 0.64 units;
- Germany has a connection with Belgium for a value of 0.64 units and with Estonia for a value of 0.55 units.

The analysis of the network structure serves to identify what are the effects of propagation of growth (or decrease) of the index of the confidence of the building manufacturers between the countries. For example, if the index of building manufacturers' trust increases (or decreases) in Germany by 1 unit, then it increases (or decreases) by 0.64 units in Belgium and increases (or decreases) by 0.55 in Estonia. Obviously, these relationships must not be considered as cause-and-effect types, on the contrary, it is simply a similar structure of the historical series of the countries analyzed.

Conclusions. The value of the building manufacturers' trusted index has decreased on average for European countries from a value of 0.53 units in March 2022 up to -3.19 in December 2022 or equal to a value of -3.73 even units A -698%. However, we can verify two trends in the average value of the building manufacturers' trusted index or: between March and October 2022 this indicator has decreased to an absolute minimum equal to -4.70, subsequently from October to December 2022 this value started to grow until you reach the value of -3.19. It follows that probably the most negative

phase of the building manufacturers' trusted index has been exceeded in October 2022. However, it is very difficult to consider the possibility of a growth in the construction sector in the adversity of the economic cycle above all due to the growth of energy costs and inflation. In fact, the construction sector generally tends to be pro-cyclic, that is, it follows the economic cycle. For this reason, it is very likely that the countries in which there is a growth in the confidence of the building manufacturers are affected by a building speculation.

Declarations

Data Availability Statement. The data presented in this study are available on request from the corresponding author.

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Declaration of Competing Interest. The author declares that there is no conflict of interests regarding the publication of this manuscript. In addition, the ethical issues, including plagiarism, informed consent, misconduct, data fabrication and/or falsification, double publication.

Software. The authors have used the following software: Gretl for the econometric models, Orange for clusterization and network analysis, and KNIME for machine learning and predictions. They are all free version without licenses.

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Appendix

Indice della fiducia dei costruttori										
Country	2022-03	2022-04	2022-05	2022-06	2022-07	2022-08	2022-09	2022-10	2022-11	2022-12
Belgium	★ 9,2	★ 8,3	★ 5,7	★ 3	★ 7	★ 2,6	★ 1,1	★ 0,7	★ 0,9	★ 0,3
Bulgaria	★ -10,3	★ -13	★ -17,8	★ -16,7	★ -15,5	★ -13,8	★ -11,8	★ -12,1	★ -10,2	★ -7,7
Czechia	★ -0,4	★ -1,2	★ -3,5	★ -4,6	★ -4,4	★ -8,6	★ -8,4	★ -8,9	★ -2,7	★ -7,6
Denmark	★ -3,6	★ -6,7	★ -7,3	★ -11,1	★ -14,3	★ -15	★ -16,5	★ -17	★ -17,3	★ -16,2
Germany	★ 9,1	★ 5,3	★ 6,5	★ 5	★ 0,6	★ 1,1	★ -3,6	★ -4	★ -2,4	★ -2,5
Estonia	★ 3,6	★ 5,4	★ 1,4	★ 2,7	★ -1,9	★ -1,8	★ -3,8	★ -3,2	★ -7,3	★ -9,3
Ireland	★ 28,2	★ 16,8	★ 14,2	★ 13,1	★ 9	★ 10,9	★ 7,3	★ 7,6	★ 12,4	★ 20,6
Greece	★ 1,1	★ -6,7	★ -24,9	★ -14,5	★ -34,6	★ -31,7	★ -29,2	★ -26,1	★ -25,9	★ -23,3
Spain	★ 9	★ 8,9	★ 21,2	★ 1,7	★ 3,9	★ 10	★ 4,9	★ 13,6	★ 12,6	★ 17,5
France	★ 5,5	★ 5,5	★ 5,3	★ 4,3	★ 2,3	★ 4,5	★ 2,8	★ 5,3	★ 4,5	★ 4,5
Croatia	★ 8,9	★ 7,7	★ 7,1	★ 8	★ 6,2	★ 8,2	★ 9,1	★ 8,2	★ 8,4	★ 7,2
Italy	★ 5,2	★ 4,8	★ 4,8	★ 5,4	★ 8,4	★ 2,5	★ 5,3	★ 4,5	★ 1,4	★ 5,5
Cyprus	★ -18,6	★ -22,5	★ -18,4	★ -17,7	★ -17,6	★ -19,6	★ -15,6	★ -22,1	★ -14,8	★ -11
Latvia	★ -14,5	★ -13,7	★ -14,8	★ -15	★ -15,8	★ -14,8	★ -16,3	★ -15,2	★ -12,5	★ -14,6
Lithuania	★ -19	★ -18,3	★ -20,5	★ -17,8	★ -17,9	★ -20,2	★ -17,3	★ -12,8	★ -11,9	★ -11,7
Luxembourg	★ 27,5	★ 30,6	★ 26,7	★ 18,5	★ 20,1	★ 19,1	★ 11,7	★ 5,8	★ 11,3	★ 10,1
Hungary	★ 1,5	★ -1,1	★ -3,8	★ -5,2	★ -1,8	★ -6,6	★ -11	★ -14,5	★ -15,2	★ -14,9
Malta	★ 3,4	★ 15,1	★ 18,1	★ 15,1	★ 5,2	★ 8,7	★ 5,9	★ -0,3	★ 2,5	★ -4,3
Netherlands	★ 23,3	★ 16,4	★ 12,1	★ 14	★ 17,6	★ 16,2	★ 14,9	★ 12,3	★ 12,9	★ 12,6
Austria	★ 20,2	★ 13,9	★ 8,7	★ 7,9	★ 5,5	★ 7,2	★ 2,4	★ 4,2	★ -1,6	★ 2,2
Poland	★ -18,7	★ -19,6	★ -20,1	★ -21,9	★ -22,9	★ -23,2	★ -23,8	★ -25	★ -24,3	★ -24,4
Portugal	★ -0,9	★ -5,6	★ -3,6	★ -8	★ -3,8	★ -6,7	★ -4,4	★ -5,1	★ -4	★ -5,5
Romania	★ -9,4	★ -9,4	★ -9,7	★ -9,3	★ -9,4	★ -9,9	★ -8,4	★ -9	★ -7,2	★ -9,1
Slovenia	★ 26,8	★ 22,6	★ 25	★ 18,9	★ 15,4	★ 16,1	★ 13,2	★ 18,6	★ 21,7	★ 24,3
Slovakia	★ -11,1	★ -22,5	★ -17	★ -18,2	★ -7,3	★ -14,8	★ -13,9	★ -10,9	★ -5,8	★ -2,9
Finland	★ 2,8	★ -1,5	★ -12,6	★ -15,1	★ -18,6	★ -15,3	★ -7,4	★ -10,1	★ -13,9	★ -16,6
Sweden	★ 14,3	★ 6	★ 6,2	★ 4,3	★ 4,1	★ 5,6	★ 4,5	★ 2,3	★ -1,2	★ -1,6
Montenegro	★ -18,9	★ -16,4	★ -0,4	★ -6,6	★ -9,3	★ -9,1	★ -9,2	★ 1,1	★ 5,1	★ 5,3
North Macedonia	★ -16,7	★ -6,7	★ -11	★ -12,9	★ -11,6	★ -4,4	★ -8,4	★ -13,3	★ -15,7	★ -12,8
Albania	★ -19,1	★ -17	★ -14,5	★ -13,8	★ -12,4	★ -8,6	★ -6,5	★ -10,2	★ -4,5	★ -7,3
Serbia	★ -1,6	★ -6,2	★ -6	★ -5,6	★ -7,1	★ -10,2	★ -6	★ -5,7	★ -2,3	★ -1,6
Türkiye	★ -19,7	★ -16,8	★ -17,7	★ -15,3	★ -13,7	★ -12,6	★ -11,8	★ -9,4	★ -8,4	★ -7,5

Media della Variazione dell'Indice di Fiducia dei Costruttori tra Marzo 2022 e Dicembre 2022

C4>C2>C3>C1

- C1
- C2
- C3
- C4

